

nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : NNMT is an enzyme that catalyzes the methylation of nicotinamide and similar compounds using the methyl donor S-adenosyl methionine (SAM-e) to produce S-adenosyl-L-homocysteine (SAH) and 1-methylnicotinamide (MNAM). Apropos MNAM, mammalian livers contain an enzyme system which can oxidize MNAM to N¹-methyl-4-pyridone-3-carboxamide (4-pyridone) and N¹-methyl-2-pyridone-5-carboxamide (2-pyridone). Many of the properties of this enzyme system are similar to those which have been reported for rabbit liver aldehyde oxidase (AOX). All three metabolites are observed to be eventually excreted in the urine. Further, NNMT is implicated in Parkinson's disease, thyroid carcinoma, renal cell carcinomas, colorectal cancer, gastric cancer, oral squamous cell carcinoma, congenital heart defects, non-small cell lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, neurone morphology, nasopharyngeal cancer, bipolar disorder, breast cancer, obesity, type 2 diabetes, urinary excretion, adenoid cystic carcinoma, prostate cancer, ovarian neoplasms, chronic kidney disease and uterine leiomyosarcomas, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a

^{*}ML dicoveries of NNMT synergy in Meningiomas

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signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of NNMT, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: NNMT, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective memberanes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT)

Nicotinamide N-methyltransferase (NNMT) (E.C. 2.1.1.1) catalyzes the methylation of nicotinamide (NAM) using the methyl donor S-adenosyl methionine (SAM-e) to

produce S-adenosyl-L-homocysteine (SAH) and 1-methylnicotinamide (MNAM). The catalysis chemical reaction is depicted in the below equation 1 -

The two substrates of this enzyme are S-adenosyl methionine and nicotinamide, while its two products are S-adenosylhomocysteine and 1-methylnicotinamide. The systematic name of this enzyme class is S-adenosyl-L-methionine:nicotinamide N-methyltransferase. NNMT belongs to the family of transferases, which transfers one-carbon group methyltransferases. A transferase is an enzyme which catalyse the transfer of specific functional groups (e.g. a methyl/glycosyl group) from one molecule (called the donor) to another (called the acceptor). Methyltransferases (can be split into several subclasses based on their structural features) are enzymes that all methylate their substrates.

Further, NNMT participates in nicotinate and nicotinamide metabolism, were Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) is a coenzyme central to metabolism and found in all living cells. NAD consists of two nucleotides joined via their phosphate groups; One nucleotide contains an adenine nucleobase and the other, nicotinamide. NAD exists in two forms: one oxidized and the other a reduced form, abbreviated as NAD^+ and NADH (H - hydrogen), respectively.

In metabolism among the cells, NAD is involved in redox reactions, carrying electrons from one reaction to another while existing in two forms - • NAD^+ is an oxidizing agent which gains electrons from other molecules and becoming reduced; • with H^+ , this reaction forms NADH, which can be used as a reducing agent to donate electrons. Such electron transfer reactions are the main function of NAD. Further, it is used as a substrate of enzymes in adding/removing chemical groups to/from proteins, in post-translational modifications (Pollak et al. [13]). NAD consists of two nucleosides joined by pyrophosphate, with each nucleoside containing a ribose ring, one with adenine attached to the first carbon atom (the 1' position) (adenosine diphosphate ribose) and the other with nicotinamide at this position. The compound accepts/donates the equivalent of H^- and involve the removal of two hydrogen atoms from a reactant (R), in the form of a proton (H^+) and a hydride ion (H^-). H^+ is released into solution, while the reductant RH_2 is oxidized and NAD^+ reduced to NADH via transfer of H^- to the nicotinamide ring, as represented in the equation 2 below -

This is depicted graphically in figure 2.

Apropos, 1-methylnicotinamide (MNAM), mammalian livers contain an enzyme system which can oxidize MNAM to N^1 -methyl-4-pyridone-3-carboxamide (4-pyridone) and N^1 -methyl-2-pyridone-5-carboxamide (2-pyridone). Many of the properties of this enzyme system are similar to those which have been reported for rabbit liver aldehyde oxidase (AOX). All three metabolites are observed to be eventually excreted in the urine. Both pyridones are made in all the mammals examined, although in varying ratios and Felsted and Chaykin [15] found observed that the ratio of the 2-pyridone to the 4-pyridone was constant for a given species. Their data have been taken as preliminary evidence in support of the concept that the two pyridones are synthesized from MNAM by a single enzyme.

Figure 2: A schematic diagram of the redox reactions of NAD by ©Tim Vickers, released under public domain (PD) at Commons [14].

Excess NAM (a form of vitamin B₃), is metabolized through two enzymatic systems and eventually excreted from the body. • The first system starts with the methylation of NAM by NNMT, which can subsequently be oxidized by AOX, while • the second enzymatic system oxidizes NAM to NAM N-oxide which is found in the endoplasmic reticulum of hepatocytes but the precise enzyme was unknown. Real et al. [16] identified CYP2E1 as the main activity producing NAM N-oxide, by using human liver microsomes in combination with selective cytochrome P450 inhibitors, specific substrates, and antibodies. Their results suggested NAM N-oxide as a potential biomarker of CYP2E1 activity from urine or blood samples.

Although baseline requirements for NAD⁺ synthesis can be met either with dietary tryptophan or with < 20 mg of daily niacin (consisting of nicotinic acid and/or NAM), there is a growing evidence that substantially greater rates of NAD⁺ synthesis might be beneficial to protect against neurological degeneration, *Candida glabrata* infection, and possibly to enhance reverse cholesterol transport. Bogan and Brenner [17] reviewed the distinct tissue-specific biosynthetic and/or ligand activities of tryptophan, NAM, nicotinic acid (NA), and NAM riboside (a newly identified NAD⁺ precursor), and found them to be responsible for vitamin-specific (side)effects. Bogan and Brenner [17] present a schematic diagram of NAD⁺ synthesis, recycling and clearance, in a figure in Box 2, of their manuscript.

Using ion-pairing radiochemical assay, Rini et al. [18] studied the biochemical properties and individual variation of human liver NNMT.

Human liver NNMT activity has a bimodal frequency distribution, an observation which raised the possibility that this enzyme activity might be regulated by a genetic polymorphism. This polymorphism could have functional implications for individual differences in drug and xenobiotic toxicity. To test this hypothesis Aksoy et al. [19]

cloned and isolated a human liver NNMT cDNA that was 969 nucleotides in length, with a 792-nucleotide open reading frame that encoded a 264-amino acid protein with a calculated molecular mass of 29.6 kDa. Further, on transfection of COS-1 cells with this construct, they observed high level of NNMT enzymatic activity, and the biochemical properties of this activity were similar to those of human liver NNMT.

Further, Aksoy et al. [20] isolated the genomic DNA clones for NNMT human chromosome 11-specific DNA library. They determined the structure of the human NNMT gene and the transcription initiation site. Also, they mapped NNMT to chromosome band 11q23.1.

1.3. Roles of NNMT in different disease

Parkinson's disease (PD) may be initiated or precipitated by endogenous toxins with a structure similar to 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine in genetically-predisposed individuals. Aoyama et al. [21] measured the protein amount of NNMT in the lumbar cerebrospinal fluid of PD patients via immunoblot analysis using anti-human NNMT antibody. They observed significantly higher relative levels of NNMT protein in younger (65 years old or younger) PD patients than that in younger controls. Further, aging affected the amount of NNMT protein as it decreased along with aging in PD patients. Their findings suggested that excess NNMT in the central nervous system might be implicated in the PD pathogenesis.

To understand the molecular pathogenesis of thyroid cancer, Xu et al. [22] used DNA microarray to study the expression profiles of 10 different human **thyroid carcinoma** cell lines (which included papillary lines BHP-2-7/7-13/10-3/18-21, NPA 87, and TPC1; anaplastic lines ARO 81-1 and DRO 90-1; follicular line WRO 82-1; and medullary line HRO 85-1). They observed increased expression of NNMT only in the papillary cell lines. While, normal thyroid tissue, thyroid primary cultures, anaplastic cancer cells, and medullary cancer cells showed no or low enzyme activity, their immunohistochemical staining for NNMT of human thyroid specimens demonstrated strong and abundant cytoplasmic reactions in the sections of papillary carcinomas, and weak/scanty reaction in the normal thyroid tissues. Thus their results indicated that NNMT was a potential biomarker for papillary thyroid carcinoma.

Yao et al. [23] examined the gene expression profiles of 33 **renal cell carcinomas** (RCCs) and nine normal kidney samples. Their hierarchical clustering demonstrated that clear-cell RCC, chromophobe RCC, and normal kidney tissue showed distinctive gene expression profiles. Among the genes whose expression was upregulated in clear-cell RCC, they selected adipose differentiation-related protein (ADFP) and (NNMT), for further analysis and found increased levels of ADFP and NNMT mRNA in clear-cell RCCs than in other non-clear-cell tumour subtypes using RT-qPCR.

Roeßler et al. [24] studied to identify and validate novel serum markers of human **colorectal cancer** as potential candidates for noninvasive detection of early colorectal neoplasm. While analyzing 16 matched colorectal cancer and adjacent normal tissue samples, they identified 735 different proteins colon tissue. Further, the confirmed strong elevation for 5 proteins in colorectal cancer, namely : transforming growth factor- β induced protein ig-h3 (β IG-H3), NNMT, nucleoside diphosphate kinase A (nm23-H1), purine nucleoside phosphorylase (PNPH), and mannose-6-phosphate receptor binding

protein 1 (M6P1). Also, they found elevated levels of NNMT in serum from patients with colorectal cancer, which was not predicted to be secreted but known as a cytoplasmic protein.

In search for potential markers for gastric cancer, Lim et al. [25] analysed tumor and normal tissues from 152 **gastric cancer** cases via two-dimensional gel electrophoresis (2-DE). On analysis of images of silver stained gels, they found that spot 4262 showed higher expression (5.7-fold increase) in cancer tissues than in normal tissues and identified it as NNMT.

Sartini et al. [26] investigated the expression levels of NNMT, in **oral squamous cell carcinoma** (OSCC) and found that NNMT was up-regulated in most of the favorable OSCCs, while no marked NNMT expression alterations between tumor and normal mucosa were detected in most of the unfavorable OSCCs.

Congenital heart defects (CHDs) have a multifactorial origin, in which subtle genetic factors and peri-conception exposures interact. van Driel et al. [27] hypothesized that derangements in the homocysteine and detoxification pathways, due to a polymorphism in the NNMT gene, low maternal dietary nicotinamide intake, and medicine use in the peri-conception period, affected CHD risk. Using 292 case and 316 control families, they concluded that children carrying the NNMT A allele face additional CHD risk in combination with peri-conception exposure to medicines and/or a low dietary nicotinamide intake.

Tomida et al. [28] established an ELISA system for NNMT and determined the levels of NNMT and carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) in sera of 113 **non-small cell lung cancer** (NSCLC) patients undergoing surgery and sera of 50 non-neoplastic lung disease patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and of 24 healthy donors. This was done with an aim to study if NNMT was useful as a biomarker of lung cancer (stages I-III), or not. They observed higher serum levels of NNMT in lung cancer patients than in COPD patients and healthy donors.

NNMT is highly expressed in quadriceps muscles of patients with **chronic obstructive pulmonary disease** (COPD) but, its expression in the diaphragm of these patients has not been assessed and the functional significance of NNMT induction in skeletal muscles of patients with COPD is also unknown. Kim et al. [29] observed elevated expressions of NNMT in the diaphragm and quadriceps muscles of patients with COPD; however, the relative induction of NNMT expression was greater in the quadriceps muscle (10-fold) than it was in the diaphragm (2-fold). Overexpression of NNMT was observed in skeletal myoblasts, NNMT expression, which was induced by IL-6, TGF- β , and TNF- α , which triggered an increase in proliferation and migration, but had no influence on cell death.

Previously, Thomas et al. [30] showed that NNMT expression protected against neurotoxin-mediated cell death by increasing Complex I (CxI) activity, thus resulting in increased ATP synthesis, which was mediated via protection of the NDUFS3 subunit of CxI from degradation by increased MeN production. Next, Thomas et al. [30] explored the effects of NNMT expression on neurone morphology and differentiation and found that expression of NNMT in SH-SY5Y human neuroblastoma and N27 rat mesencephalic dopaminergic neurones increased neurite branching, synaptophysin expression and dopamine accumulation and release. Their results showed that NNMT expression regulated **neurone morphology** in vitro by the sequential activation of the

EFNB2 and AKT cellular signalling pathways.

NNMT was first identified as a differentially upregulated gene in **nasopharyngeal cancer** tissues via data mining from published transcriptomic databases and since no prior study had attempted to evaluate the clinical significance of NNMT or phosphorylated AKT (pAKT) expression in nasopharyngeal cancer, Win et al. [31] explored their expression in a large cohort of patients with nasopharyngeal cancer. Their study included pathological slides of 124 nasopharyngeal cancer patients who were free of distant metastasis at initial diagnosis. They observed high expression of both markers associated with an increment of tumor stage and positive correlation between NNMT and pAKT expression.

Sazci et al. [32] reported the association of the rs694539 variant of NNMT gene with **bipolar disorder** in a case-control study of 95 bipolar disorder patients and 201 healthy controls.

Zhang et al. [33] showed that NNMT was selectively expressed in some **breast cancer** cell lines, and down-regulation of NNMT expression in Bcap-37 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines by NNMT shRNA significantly inhibited cell growth in vitro, decreased tumorigenicity in mice and induced apoptosis. Vice versa, they confirmed the silencing reciprocal effect of NNMT by over-expressing NNMT in the MCF-7 and SK-BR-3 breast cancer cell lines which lacked constitutive expression of NNMT. Their results suggested that down-regulation of NNMT induced apoptosis via the mitochondria-mediated pathway in breast cancer cells.

In **obesity and type 2 diabetes**, GLUT4 glucose transporter expression is decreased selectively in adipocytes. Adipose-specific knockout or overexpression of Glut4 alters systemic insulin sensitivity. Kraus et al. [34] showed that NNMT was the most strongly reciprocally regulated gene when comparing gene expression in white adipose tissue (WAT) from adipose-specific GLUT4-knockout or adipose-specific GLUT4-overexpressing mice with their respective controls. It is known that SAM provides propylamine for polyamine biosynthesis and donates a methyl group for histone methylation. Polyamine flux including synthesis, catabolism and excretion, is controlled by the rate-limiting enzymes ornithine decarboxylase (ODC) and spermidine-spermine N¹-acetyltransferase (SSAT; encoded by SAT1) and by polyamine oxidase (PAO), and has a major role in energy metabolism. Further, they reported that NNMT expression was increased in WAT and liver of obese and diabetic mice and its knockdown in WAT and liver protected against diet-induced obesity by augmenting cellular energy expenditure. They also observed that the inhibition increased adipose SAM and NAD⁺ levels and upregulated ODC and SSAT activity as well as expression, owing to the effects of NNMT on histone H3 lysine 4 methylation in adipose tissue. Direct evidence for increased polyamine flux resulting from NNMT inhibition included elevated **urinary excretion** and adipocyte secretion of diacetylspermine, a product of polyamine metabolism.

The malignant tumor **adenoid cystic carcinoma** (AdCC) occurs in the salivary glands and frequently metastasizes. The aim of this study was to identify factors mediating AdCC metastasis. Ishibashi et al. [35] observed significant altered processes in lymph node metastatic (ACCS-LN-GFP) cells, mainly the increased expression of NNMT.

You et al. [36] investigated the expression of NNMT in the peripheral blood of patients with **prostate cancer** (PCa) and of healthy control subjects and their results

showed an increase in the expression level of the same in the peripheral blood and tissues of patients with PCa. They further observed that the overexpression of NNMT enhanced PC-3 cell viability, invasion and migration capacity. Additionally, they observed that the overexpression of NNMT increased the mRNA level of sirtuin 1 (SIRT1) in PC-3 cells.

In a first, Harmankaya et al. [37] examined the expression of NNMT in serous ovarian cystadenomas, serous borderline tumours, low grade serous carcinomas (LGSC) and high grade serous carcinomas (HGSC) and investigated the potential independent association of NNMT expression with survival. Their study suggested that NNMT was progressively overexpressed in the stroma of **ovarian neoplasms** from benign cysts to HGSCs.

Dysregulation of NAD^+ metabolism contributes to the initiation and progression of age-associated diseases, including **chronic kidney disease** (CKD). Takahashi et al. [38] generated NNMT-deficient mice and a unilateral ureter obstruction (UUO) model and conducted two clinical studies on human CKD to investigate the role of NNMT in CKD and fibrosis. They observed that the increased renal NNMT expression induced NAD^+ and methionine metabolism perturbation and contributed to renal fibrosis.

Uterine leiomyosarcomas (uLMS) are extremely rare high-grade tumors and the uterus is the most frequent site for LMS. uLMS and uterine leiomyoma (uLM) must frequently be differentiated in patients with a uterine mass. In a first, Türkmen et al. [39] study the NNMT expression in uLMS, uLM and benign uterine myometrium and correlated NNMT overexpression with worse prognosis in uLMS. They observed that the expression of NNMT in uLMS was markedly higher than in uLM and normal myometrial tissue.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as

unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [40] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [41] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [41].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [42]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a

sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [43], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [40] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [40]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [44], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method).

25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command *source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")*. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. NNMT related synergies

Note - NNMT was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of NNMT were recorded.

3.1.1. NNMT - individual genes

The following genes in combination with NNMT showed high rankings - prominin 1 (PROM1), neuron navigator 3 (NAV3), LIM and cysteine rich domains 1 (LMCD1), solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked

(SRPX), transmembrane protein 59 like (TMEM59L), MINDY lysine 48 deubiquitinase 4 (MINDY4), neurexin 2 (NRXN2), GLI family zinc finger 1 (GLI1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), podocalyxin like 2 (PODXL2), solute carrier family 30 member 3 (SLC30A3), hippocalcin like 4 (HPCAL4), tripartite motif containing 67 (TRIM67), collagen type X alpha 1 chain (COL10A1), proteolipid protein 1 (PLP1), RUNX family transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), serpin family F member 1 (SERPINF1), peripherin (PRPH), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), dual oxidase 1 (DUOX1), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), retinol binding protein 4 (RBP4), dual oxidase maturation factor 1 (DUOX1), fibroblast growth factor 7 (FGF7), NKD inhibitor of WNT signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 3 subunit (CHRN3), dopamine receptor D2 (DRD2), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 6 (KCNA6), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), phosphodiesterase 1C (PDE1C), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), frizzled related protein (FRZB), C1q and TNF related 7 (C1QTNF7), Rho related BTB domain containing 3 (RHOBTB3), transmembrane protein 130 (TMEM130), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4 / ODAD2), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cy-

tochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase and protein isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A / NALF1), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of NNMT with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t NNMT with NNMT – > PROM1 / NAV3 / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 / SRPX / TMEM59L / MINDY4 / NRXN2 / GLI1 / NPR3 / PODXL2 / SLC30A3 / HPCAL4 / TRIM67 / COL10A1 / PLP1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / KIF1A / SERPINF1 / PRPH / SCN7A / DUOX1 / LHCGR / RBP4 / DUOXA1 / FGF7 / NKD1 / NXPH2 / CHRNB3 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / PID1 / PDE1C / S100B / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / RHOBTB3 / TMEM130 / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / MACROD2 / IL17D / PEAK1 / SUSP5 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 / SLC3A1 / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / STK31 / MME / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS NNMT									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T NNMT									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
PROM1 - NNMT	280	266	322	24	NAV3 - NNMT	257	212	236	71
LMCD1 - NNMT	259	279	241	10	SLC12A1 - NNMT	286	249	267	131
SRPX - NNMT	315	209	291	8	TMEM59L - NNMT	233	261	203	22
MINDY4 - NNMT	213	225	96	204	NRXN2 - NNMT	236	200	224	59
GLI1 - NNMT	241	217	218	52	NPR3 - NNMT	307	237	251	32
PODXL2 - NNMT	247	222	281	16	SLC30A3 - NNMT	278	215	234	14
HPCAL4 - NNMT	244	206	228	36	TRIM67 - NNMT	197	260	295	1
COL10A1 - NNMT	251	238	261	33	PLP1 - NNMT	285	247	248	18
RUNX2 - NNMT	208	250	226	101	LAMP5 - NNMT	388	270	313	392
KIF1A - NNMT	324	265	260	28	SERPINF1 - NNMT	230	226	288	23
PRPH - NNMT	276	268	275	15	SCN7A - NNMT	277	201	269	12
DUOX1 - NNMT	258	258	208	21	LHCGR - NNMT	294	243	302	97
RBP4 - NNMT	345	278	287	153	DUOX1 - NNMT	275	208	277	44
FGF7 - NNMT	343	257	331	390	NKD1 - NNMT	301	251	262	139
NXP2 - NNMT	329	281	243	389	CHRNA3 - NNMT	302	210	303	37
DRD2 - NNMT	271	259	266	40	KCNA6 - NNMT	235	280	274	63
PID1 - NNMT	254	264	276	38	PDE1C - NNMT	292	231	358	116
S100B - NNMT	288	228	298	148	FRZB - NNMT	255	203	264	109
C1QTNF7 - NNMT	295	245	263	3	RHOBTB3 - NNMT	207	262	239	20
TMEM130 - NNMT	334	267	362	391	LDHD - NNMT	362	375	388	354
PRRT2 - NNMT	245	320	314	157	CYP2S1 - NNMT	344	377	349	296
NT5DC2 - NNMT	387	374	392	317	FILIP1L - NNMT	356	356	385	347
RAB31 - NNMT	369	347	311	334	NPNT - NNMT	333	333	324	319
ATO8 - NNMT	301	331	377	304	VAMP5 - NNMT	328	322	382	247
ENHO - NNMT	293	340	327	72	ARMC4 - NNMT	384	319	344	198
CPT1C - NNMT	297	276	318	100	CCDC126 - NNMT	353	373	321	329
GPR183 - NNMT	377	309	342	375	ITGAM - NNMT	331	328	373	343
GPR27 - NNMT	282	314	329	226	MAP6 - NNMT	354	318	367	185
MACROD2 - NNMT	376	361	372	318	IL17D - NNMT	363	335	345	265
PEAK1 - NNMT	374	353	347	340	SUSD5 - NNMT	269	304	305	152
HEG1 - NNMT	321	307	339	323	HOXB2 - NNMT	290	312	285	118
CD248 - NNMT	311	339	333	207	DNAH12 - NNMT	224	337	294	169
P2RY14 - NNMT	263	302	371	146	YPEL2 - NNMT	355	376	383	363

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between NNMT VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic NNMT 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of NNMT-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS NNMT									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T NNMT									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
FAM131A - NNMT	358	392	363	277	CABP4 - NNMT	327	283	355	270
SLCO3A1 - NNMT	222	289	354	184	MAMSTR - NNMT	284	365	370	238
FZD8 - NNMT	378	380	306	361	MYOZ1 - NNMT	352	324	359	194
PDE4DIP - NNMT	373	372	361	337	CSRNP3 - NNMT	365	386	300	249
CIITA - NNMT	392	369	319	298	KCNE1 - NNMT	314	389	348	269
NME9 - NNMT	340	303	353	208	PLAG1 - NNMT	313	385	378	377
EXT1 - NNMT	337	323	375	321	BGN - NNMT	375	357	335	233
EPHB3 - NNMT	323	343	389	305	PLCB1 - NNMT	351	300	282	140
PYCR1 - NNMT	349	368	337	360	NEB - NNMT	370	362	379	219
FAM43B - NNMT	279	345	357	220	TMEM119 - NNMT	338	349	308	93
OLFML1 - NNMT	310	348	350	160	DUSP5P1 - NNMT	281	366	296	168
ADRA2C - NNMT	283	334	310	223	PRKD1 - NNMT	249	341	220	85
CSF1 - NNMT	391	316	384	306	FLRT2 - NNMT	379	313	387	212
PRKG1 - NNMT	385	391	351	235	SHC4 - NNMT	316	305	312	155
CYP4Z1 - NNMT	326	330	299	302	CYP4X1 - NNMT	367	390	336	332
RTN4RL2 - NNMT	347	367	386	299	C2orf88 - NNMT	386	355	326	278
KBTBD12 - NNMT	303	301	341	222	LDLRAD2 - NNMT	309	326	286	73
ENTPD8 - NNMT	304	306	309	195	PLAC9 - NNMT	209	297	366	66
NUGGC - NNMT	240	310	374	174	STK31 - NNMT	348	370	369	309
MME - NNMT	212	269	213	83	DACT3 - NNMT	336	298	365	300
ADARB1 - NNMT	390	382	356	253	SPN - NNMT	357	360	307	284
C2orf27A - NNMT	339	387	391	374	CLEC9A - NNMT	341	295	315	143
MT1F - NNMT	364	358	297	282	ITGBL1 - NNMT	380	379	381	362
MMP17 - NNMT	266	292	317	108	DLL1 - NNMT	274	362	293	150
ZNF521 - NNMT	256	290	280	35	RYR3 - NNMT	312	294	258	98
DUSP27 - NNMT	359	384	343	307	RNU6-529P - NNMT	368	378	325	271
SYT15 - NNMT	300	353	346	234	FAM155A - NNMT	330	336	233	142
TMEM240 - NNMT	366	329	259	209	ANKRD20A9P - NNMT	232	287	211	62
HACD2 - NNMT	332	388	390	310	GPX3 - NNMT	299	332	242	88
HMGB3P7 - NNMT	239	288	328	112	TENM3 - NNMT	250	282	229	54
RFPL1S - NNMT	342	342	380	193	LINC00937 - NNMT	389	383	368	357
LINC01907 - NNMT	350	338	352	369	ITGB2-AS1 - NNMT	325	346	332	166
LMCD1-AS1 - NNMT	320	350	272	214	ZNF883 - NNMT	382	344	360	311

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between NNMT VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t NNMT	
PROM1 / NAV3 / LMCD1 / SLC12A1 / SRPX ...	
TMEM59L / MINDY4 / NRXN2 / GLI1 / NPR3 ...	
PODXL2 / SLC30A3 / HPCAL4 / TRIM67 ...	
COL10A1 / PLP1 / RUNX2 / LAMP5 / KIF1A ...	
SERPINF1 / PRPH / SCN7A / DUOX1 / LHCGR ...	
RBP4 / DUOXA1 / FGF7 / NKD1 / NXPH2 ...	
CHRNA3 / DRD2 / KCNA6 / PID1 / PDE1C ...	
S100B / FRZB / C1QTNF7 / RHOBTB3 ...	
TMEM130 / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 ...	
NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 ...	
VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126 ...	
GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / MACROD2 ...	
IL17D / PEAK1 / SUSD5 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 ...	
DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 ...	
SLCO3A1 / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP ...	
CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 ...	
EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / PYCR1 / NEB ...	
SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 ...	
KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC ...	
STK31 / MME / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A ...	
CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 ...	
ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 ...	
FAM155A / TMEM240 / ANKRD20A9P / HACD2 ...	
GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 ...	
LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883	NNMT

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between NNMT and Individual members.

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